

A Questionnaire Survey to Examine Married Rural Women's Knowledge of Various Contraceptive Methods.

Priyadarshini

Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India.

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Corresponding author: Dr. Priyadarshini

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study is to assess the awareness towards various contraceptive devices among married rural women. **Methods:** A prospective observational study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India for 12 months. A total of 200 women of the age group of 16 – 45 years were included in the study. The preformed questionnaire was prepared by the two qualified personal. All the study included participants were asked a series of question from the preformed questionnaire. All the questions were asked in the local language. The questionnaire did consist of two parts. The first part of questionnaire consists of detail demographic history and the second part consists of awareness related to emergency contraceptives. **Results:** Of the total 200 women, the literacy rate was found in 170 women and rest of the 30 women were found to be illiterate. Those who were aware or had the knowledge related to the EC, only those women were further questioned for the depth of knowledge and awareness related to emergency contraceptives. The present study states that around 88.5% women have heard and had some or the other knowledge related to the emergency contraceptives. The reason for this is the main source of information was found to be television and friends and social media. When the question related to the source of knowledge and information was asked television was found to be the main source of information followed by friends and husbands and social media. In context to the questions related to the time of consumption of Emergency contraceptive pills, majority of them had no idea about the ideal time for the taking Emergency contraceptive pills. **Conclusion:** Based on the findings, it is concluded that on an average majority of women have adequate knowledge of emergency contraception as a whole. Majority of them are likely to have mix attitude towards Emergency contraception.

Keywords: contraceptives, social media, pills

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Introduction

The meaning of contraception is to prevent the sperm to unite with the ovum, which results in failure in implantation of fertilized ovum with uterus.[1] Annually

60,000 women died globally due to pregnancy related causes and about 75,000 died due to unsafe abortion.[2,3] Out of these, 20000 women died due to lack or

failure of contraceptive devices. As a result of these unintended births, women suffered many physical and mental health problems.[4,5] One of the study done by population action international in developing countries that due to increase in spacing between births, there was a decrease in two third infant mortality rate.[6] So, to increase the spacing between the births, Family Planning methods should be made accessible and available to all reproductive population so that they responsibly decide about when and how many children they have (by choice and not by chance).[7] The Family Welfare Programme in India is a centrally sponsored programme/scheme to reduce the unwanted pregnancies with the introduction of contraceptives. As a result, it can reduce the maternal mortality because of reduction in high-risk pregnancies as well as abortions.[8] It has been observed that with the use of modern contraceptives, we can prevent one-third of maternal deaths.[9]

Materials and methods

A prospective observational study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India for 12 months, after taking the approval of the protocol review committee and institutional ethics committee

A total of 200 women of the age group of 16 – 45 years were included in the study. The women who were over or under age other than the age range were excluded from the study. The women who were unwilling to participate also were excluded from study.

The preformed questionnaire was prepared by the two qualified personal. All the study included participants were asked a series of question from the preformed questionnaire. All the questions were asked in the local language. All the workers were trained to ask the question in the normal yet confidential manner. The informed consent was taken from all the participants.

The ethical committee of the institution was informed about the study and the ethical clearance certificate was obtained from it.

The questionnaire did consist of two parts. The first part of questionnaire consists of detail demographic history and the second part consists of awareness related to emergency contraceptives. Knowledge, administration, side effects and availability information were assessed. Various perceptions like fear and myths were also noted as the best of the knowledge.

Knowledge regarding Emergency contraception effect on sexual behaviour and fertility in general was also evaluated. After the questionnaire, opportunistic counselling was done and people were encouraged to ask queries and encouraged to get further awareness from the investigating team. Information on benefits of Emergency contraception methods, correct usage, timing, clearing doubts regarding Emergency contraception methods, and queries regarding regular contraception were also discussed.

Statistical analysis

The recorded data was compiled and entered in a spreadsheet computer program (Microsoft Excel 2007) and then exported to data editor page of SPSS version 20 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA). For analysis, the variables were summarized using descriptive summary measures, expressed as mean for continuous variables, and percentage for categorical variables.

Results

A total of 200 were included in the study. The socioeconomic data of the women who participated in the study were recorded with detail history and summarize in the Table 1. Of the total 200 women, the literacy rate was found in 170 women were as rest of the 30 women were found to be illiterate. Owing to the background 200 women were found to be from rural area and no women were from

urban area. When the question related to occupation was asked, majority of the women were house wife. Regarding their family background majority of them use to live in joint family. When questions pertaining to knowledge and usage of Emergency contraception were asked,

majority of them were aware of usage of emergency contraceptives. Those who were aware or had the knowledge related to the Emergency contraception, only those women were further questioned for the depth of knowledge and awareness related to emergency contraceptives.

Table 1: Demographic data of the women participants

Variables / characteristics	No. of women=200	%age
Age		
Below 20	98	49
20-30	61	30.5
Above 30	41	20.5
Place of residence		
Rural	200	100
Urban	0	0
Socioeconomic status		
Higher	40	20
Middle	105	52.5
Lower	55	27.5
Education level		
Literate	170	85
Illiterate	30	15
Occupation of women		
House wife	148	74
Service	20	10
Labour	32	16
Type of family		
Nuclear	19	9.5
Joint	181	90.5

Second part of questioner was related to the emergency contraceptives. Majority of the women knew only about the contraceptive pills as the method, very few were aware about the IUD methods. Of those who were aware of the contraceptives pills, many of them have used it. When the question related to the source of knowledge and information was asked television was found to be the main source of information followed by friends and husbands and social media. In context

to the questions related to the time of consumption of Emergency contraception pills, majority of them had no idea about the ideal time for the taking EC pills. Some of the women had misconception related to the use of herbs and spices taken after unprotected sex can prevent their pregnancy. Participants were encouraged to disseminate the information of Emergency contraception given to them to other women and majority of them agreed to do so.

Table 2: Women's awareness in relation to emergency contraceptives

Characteristic variables for ECknowledge	No. of women	Percentage
Ever heard about the emergency contraceptives?		
Yes	177	88.5
No	23	12.5
Have ever used EC pills?		
Yes	165	82.5
No	35	17.5
Awareness of EC methods available?		
IUD	22	11
Pills	171	85.5
Others	7	3.5
Source of information related to EC		
Television	189	94.5
Friends	111	55.5
Husband	97	48.5
Social media	44	22
Proper time to take EC pills awareness?		
Before UPSI	12	6
Within 72 hours	14	7
More than 72 hours	5	2.5
Don't know	159	79.5

Discussion

Unintended pregnancies contribute to the rapid population growth that impairs desperately needed social and economic progress. If family planning programs are not strengthened and nor successful, and if current fertility were to remain unchanged, world population would increase in size.[10]

Although India was the first country in the world to introduce a National Family planning programme as early as during the first five-year plan (1951-1956) to control population explosion. The unmet need for family planning among currently married women is still 13 percent in India. Although in India it is estimated that CPR is 56% only 10% are using spacing methods. Numerous contraceptive techniques both temporary and permanent have been introduced by family welfare department of India. [11,12]

The present study was conducted in the section of rural area of Bihar population. Majority of the women were aware of the emergency contraceptives in the current study.

About the 200 women have heard about the emergency contraceptives. In a study by Myer et al, overall awareness was found to be 30% in a cohort of women in South Africa.

Prevention of these unplanned pregnancies will go a long way in improving the reproductive health of women in India as failure rate of Emergency Contraception is varying from 0-2.4% depending on the method used interval between coitus and method use and relationship of coitus to ovulation. But all methods are ineffective once implantation has already occurred. [11, 13]

The present study states that around 88.5% women have heard and had some or the other knowledge related to the emergency contraceptives. The reason of this that main source of information was found to be television and friends and social media. Friends and family members were also found to be source of information but that source was found to be unreliable and the amount of information obtained is also less. In the present study the family source and the friends' percentage as the source was found to be

very less. Awareness of Emergency contraception is poor even among the general practitioners and specialist doctors and young interns are aware of EC, but they lack an accurate and detailed knowledge regarding its composition, dosage schedule and efficacy. Patients rarely seek help in cases of condom failure and unprotected intercourse.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it is concluded that on an average majority of women have adequate knowledge on emergency contraception as a whole. Majority of them are likely to have mix attitude towards EC. There is a need for aggressive advocacy about female reproductive health and dissemination of information on family planning methods among the reproductive females. However the improvement of woman's knowledge about specific details of the method and timely utilization of emergency contraception is still required.

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